

THE NEED TO CREATE AN ALTERNATIVE ENERGY SYSTEM IN ELIMINATING ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEMS

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada energetika sohasida amalga oshirilayotgan keng ko‘lamli amaliy vazifalar, muqobil energiyadan foydalanish samaradorligi, qayta tiklanuvchi manbalardan foydalanish, bugungi kunda davlat siyosatining ustuvor vazifalariga aylanib borayotgani ta’kidlanadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Ta’lim, fan, ekologik muammolar, energiya tizimi.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена информация о широком спектре практических задач, решаемых в сфере энергетики, эффективности использования альтернативной энергетики, использования возобновляемых источников энергии, что в настоящее время становится приоритетными задачами государственной политики, затронуто.

Ключевые слова: Образование, наука, экологические проблемы, энергетическая система.

Abstract: In this article, the information on the wide range of practical tasks carried out in the field of energy, the effectiveness of the use of alternative energy, the use of renewable sources, which is currently becoming the priority tasks of the state policy, is touched upon.

Key words: Education, science, environmental problems, energy system.

The increasing number of environmental problems on earth over the next forty years has been causing serious concern to specialist scientists. The main reason for this is the increased use of energy for economic development purposes. The user of organic types of fuel sees serious depletion of the environment due to harmful gases coming out of power and heat stations, increasingly internal combustion engines. [1]

However, the processes of rising temperature are associated with gas emissions coming out of thermal power plants that use organic types of combustion into the atmosphere. In this regard, it is worth paying attention to another argument. In the next forty years, even more fuel was extracted than the organic fuel extracted throughout the entire history of mankind. [2]

Today, the amount of use of natural gas per year is 12 billion tons of oil equivalent of the world (t.n.e.) GA1 is coming true. Every year, a severe decrease in the reserves of natural resources, such as oil, natural gas, coal, uranium, on account of production and use, seriously worries mankind. [3]

It is known that the consequences of environmental disasters also negatively affect the lifestyle of millions of people living in the Aral Sea basin. The tragedy of the island aggravated

the continental climate, as a result of which the drought on the summer days increased, and the cold days of winter, on the contrary, lengthened. On the island, the number of days when the summer temperature exceeds 40 degrees has increased. [4,5]

According to experts' forecasts, by 2035- 2050 years, the air temperature in the region can again increase by 1,5–3 degrees. To date, a new "Aralqum" desert has appeared on an area of 5,0 million hectares in the dried up part of the Aral Sea. From time to time, storms are rising here and millions of tons of salt, dust and sand are reaching areas of hundreds of kilometers. [6,7]

In order to accelerate economic development, progress and have a democratic process that does not harm the environment, the world needs an environmentally friendly and affordable source of energy. It is worthwhile to approach this problem with entrepreneurship and solve it by changing technologies and supporting local initiatives. [8,9]

The use of an abundant, affordable, environmentally friendly and robust source of energy is one of the most important challenges facing the current dacha. State, Small Business and private entrepreneurs and non-profit organizations, relying on traditional research in the field of environmentally friendly energy, reduce spending on oil wealth will benefit the whole world. [10,11]

Embarking on the solution of this problem - the country will strengthen its energy security, reduce air pollution and withstand climate change. The effectiveness of the measures taken in this area is reflected in strategic goals, such as the strengthening of a democratic culture and the construction of a democratic society, where there is self-government. [12,13]

So what to do and what to do when the reserves of natural resources are severely declining year after year on a global scale? This question is answered by scientists and experts as "the time of productive use of renewable energy sources has already reached". In developed countries of the world, this resource is used productively. For example, it can be observed in Germany, England and a number of other countries. [14,15]

Renewable energy sources are very handy for those who live far from centralized energy supply (fields, pastoral steppes, seasonal-run expeditions, villages and neighborhoods that are difficult to deliver energy, etc.). In addition, this resource is of great importance in ensuring the energy security of the country, saving hydrocarbon resources in cities, that is, in crowded addresses of residents. [16,17]

There are three main reasons that force the widespread use of renewable energy sources in market conditions:

The first is considered as a national energy security, the sources of renewable energy due to the reduction in minerals such as oil, gas, coal are sources of energy within the country, while the above type is a source of fuel consumption reduction.

The second is a possible risk caused by climate change. At the same time that a renewable energy source can help meet the energy need, reducing the release of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere. As is known from the Press data of scientists, greenhouse gases, that is, carbon dioxide (SO₂) gas and methane, are increasingly found in the lower atmospheric layer of the Earth. An increase in the amount of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere leads to a rise in temperature in the Earth's atmosphere. Proceeding from the above, scientists argue that the rise in temperature can lead to unexpected negative consequences, at the same time, in order to solve these problems, it is necessary to take appropriate measures. [18]

Thirdly, another reason forcing it in market conditions is that the cost of some alternative energy sources has been declining over the last decade. The reduction in the costs of alternative energy sources can be explained by the fact that its production technology is improving. With the development of this sector, the costs are further reduced.

In the second decade of the new century, environmentally friendly pure energy technologies are changing the energy supply of our homes, enterprises and vehicles. In the next ten, twenty years, there may be even more radical changes, as the pace of use of environmentally friendly energy and the world market are accelerating.

Renewable energy in this regard is another sign of the large market spread. In short, evidence and proof are enough, and they are "green" in favor of energy, highly reliable. The probability of an environmentally friendly energy system is diverse, at the same time, new technologies make it possible to use it more widely. In particular, ethanol with cellulose; elements of hydrogen collar; the next generation of Atomic Energy, photovoltaic solar cells and stations that almost do not emit coal emissions are re-directing the economies of the countries of the world to supply a more environmentally friendly alternative energy source. [19]

Although renewable energy sources are initially invested in a somewhat significant amount in the use of devices, they are economically justified. Thanks to the traditional fuel-powered energetics, sulfur, nitrogen, carbon oxides emitted into the air are distributed over a long distance. In addition, they are added with rainwater, turning into acid compounds, and in the composition of rain falling on the Earth, negatively affecting plants, soil. As a result of the increased content of such acids in the environment, heavy metals affect the food and, ultimately, the human body through these products. In this brings with it also a loss of one damage a second. [20,21]

Renewable energy sources, which are environmentally friendly, do not cause harm to the environment. It should be said that these sources are generally not able to provide a sufficiently large population of addresses and large industrial enterprises in full. They provide energy to the remote village, neighborhood, small structures. The use of environmentally friendly renewable energy sources in our country has great prospects and is also environmentally friendly, socially and economically effective.

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